

A LOOK AT THE HISTORY OF LAW REGARDING THE EMERGENCE OF THE INVESTIGATIVE ACT OF PRODUCTION FOR RECOGNITION

Ummatov Mamarasul Tursunovich

The responsible officer of the Ministry of Internal Affairs

Safarova Dilbar Baxrilla qizi

Cadet of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs

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If we pay attention to the comments given in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" about showing in order to recognize, then the dictionary meaning of the term "Recognize" is explained as "To know, to distinguish someone, something that belongs to oneself or is familiar by its appearance or some other sign¹." Although this notion is not juridical it coincides for content of presentation for recognition investigative activity in the Criminal procedure Code.

Determining the improving prospects of showing in order to recognition investigative action in the criminal proceedings and reveal more deeply its procedural and legal significance requires to learn the stages of development of this investigative action and its social necessity.

Procedural rules of presentation for recognition have progressed until the date. Historical sources and a number of legal literature contain information on the fact that in the ancient states that originally existed in the territory of our country, criminal proceedings were carried out on the basis² of customary law and Sharia norms³. Customary law was regulated on the basis of the book "Avesta"⁴, which is the main source of Zoroastrian religion and was in practice until the 7th-8th centuries BC. According to the norms of customary law defined in "Avesta", "confessions of the guilty, statements of witnesses, swearing and others are recognized as evidence in court⁵. Various tortures were used, such as fire, hot iron pressing, melting lead on the chest during the trial"⁶. Sharia norms

¹ Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати — Т ҳарфи [Электрон манба] // URL: http://n.ziyouz.com/books/uzbek_tilining_izohli_lugati/O'zbek%20tilining%20izohli%20lug'ati%20-%20T.pdf (мурожаат қилинган вақт: 22.12.2019).

² Муродов Б.Б., Дўстмуродов У.И. Жиноят ишлари тугатиш асосларининг вужудга келиши ва ривожланиш босқичлари // Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ички ишлар вазирлиги Академиясининг ахборотномаси. – 2017. – № 4. – Б. 25-26.

³ «Авесто»нинг ўзбек тилидаги таржимасида «Вандидод». Қаранг: Авесто. Тарихий-адабий ёдгорлик. Асқад Маҳкам таржимаси. – Тошкент: «Шарқ», 2001. – 106-б.; Раҳмонов А. Шариатда инсон ҳуқуқлари // Ҳуқуқ–Право–Law. – Т., 1999. – № 3. – Б. 79.

⁴ Раҳмонов Р.И. «Авеста» – великий историко-правовой источник // Проблемы современной науки и образования. 2013. – № 2 (16). С. 132-133.

⁵ Мўминов М.Э. Жиноят процессида далилларни расмийлаштиришнинг процессуал шакллари (тарихий жиҳат) // Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ички ишлар вазирлиги Академиясининг ахборотномаси. – 2010. – № 4. – Б. 77.

⁶ Одиқориев Ҳ.Т., Азизов Н.П., Мадиримов Ҳ.Р. Давлат ва ҳуқуқ тарихи: ИИВ Олий таълим муассасалари учун дарслик. – Т.: Ўзбекистон Республикаси ИИВ Академияси, 2013. – 24-б.

are based on Muslim law and are regulated based on four sources (the Holy Qur'an, Hadiths, Ijma and Qiyas)⁷. In the state court cases were conducted by judges and military cases were considered by military judges⁸ so there were no concepts of investigative action or preliminary investigation⁹ and the work of the supreme court was under the strict control of the khan and amir during these periods¹⁰.

The analysis of legal sources related to the history of the state and law shows that, the issues of crime and punishment are regulated by custom and sharia norms as well as legal norms adopted in the name of the law or equivalent to them in some state structures in the territory of our country.

Although the examples of the statehood of the ancient Turkic people have not arrived to us entirely, such documents include the "Yaso Laws" created in 1206, the "Temur Tuzuklari", which is considered the largest code of secular legislation, the manuals of the Uzbek khans from the main rules of Sharia (for example, Suluk-al muluk). Moreover, it is sufficient to indicate the existence of legal norms which provide for punishments not implied in Sharia established by the court orally or with written decrees on criminal punishment issues in the khanates¹¹.

If we take a look at the literature on Muslim law, it can be seen that in the state structures of the Republic of Uzbekistan, although showing for recognition was not widely used as an investigative action, some of its elements existed even in those times. For example, it can be observed that the population complained about mainly regarding the restoration of their property rights to the judges and the cases where the claimant recognized and showed his lost property, i.e. objects, served as the most important evidence in such cases.

In particular, "Khidaya" is commentary book on Muslim law, a person who complains to the court to demand property recovery is considered a plaintiff and he must show the amount of the damage caused to him then he must recognize and show these items without the help of anyone¹². These actions were carried out during the interrogation process in the presence of the judge.

Certainly, even though the stolen items that needed to be identified in those times did not fully correspond to the investigative action of presenting for

⁷ Қаранг: *Исхаков С.А.* Мусулмон ҳуқуқи: ИИВ Олий таълим муассасалари учун дарслик. – Т.: Ўзбекистон Республикаси ИИВ Академияси, 2012. – 41-51-б.

⁸ *Одилқориев Ҳ.Т., Азизов Н.П., Мадиримов Ҳ.Р.* Давлат ва ҳуқуқ тарихи: ИИВ Олий таълим муассасалари учун дарслик. – Т.: Ўзбекистон Республикаси ИИВ Академияси, 2013. – 119-б.

⁹ Қаранг: *Абдумажидов Г.* Развитие законодательства о расследовании преступлений. – Т., 1974. – С. 5.

¹⁰ Қаранг: *Бакиров Ф.* Чор Туркистонида суд, шариат ва одат. – Т., 1967. – Б. 30.

¹¹ *Муқимов З.* Ўзбекистон давлати ва ҳуқуқ тарихи. Олий ўқув юртлари талабалари учун дарслик. – Т.: «Адолат», 2003. – Б. 97, 137.

¹² Қаранг: *Хидоя: Комментарий мусульманского права.* – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 1994. – Б. 54-

identification which is carried out in judicial investigation practice today the above information allows us to conclude that the act of presenting for recognition was observed in the practice of judges in state structures in the territory of our republic.

After the territory of our country was transferred to the administration of Tsarist Russia, a number of legal acts were adopted in the field of criminal justice proceedings, but these documents did not prohibit the use of Sharia and customary norms by the courts¹³.

Later, codified laws such as the Criminal Procedure Code of the RSFSR in 1922¹⁴ and the two Criminal Procedure Codes of the Uzbek SSR in 1926¹⁵ and in 1929¹⁶ were adopted, but in these procedural documents, the act of presenting for recognition was not defined as an investigative act. It can even be seen that the act of production for recognition was not defined as an investigative act even in the 1864 "Regulations of Court Proceedings"¹⁷.

However, the analysis of some legal literature shows that the criminal procedure code of the RSFSR of 1922, the two criminal procedure codes of the Uzbek SSR of 1926 and 1929 do not define the act of showing for recognition as an investigative act, but in fact it was a judicial act several years before the adoption of these procedural documents. It shows that it is used in the process of proof as a procedural act formalized by the "deed of presentation for identification in the preliminary investigation"¹⁸ in investigative practice.

After all, in those times it was necessary to conduct the act of presentation for recognition in the practice of judicial investigation but the practitioners conducted it as part of another investigation or procedural action.

Furthermore, the procedural basis for conducting this action is not defined in the codified law however in the statutory regulatory documents.

In particular, it can be seen that in 1926, the Presidium of the Supreme Court of the RSFSR in its instruction on the practice of considering criminal cases of invasion established procedural rules to the tune: "Recognition is a key and common piece of evidence in burglary cases, but this action is often conducted under uncomfortable conditions which its result will not be adequately expressed in the records of inquiry and investigation. Victim identification of the perpetrator

¹³ Қаранг: Абдумажидов Г. Развитие законодательства о расследовании преступлений. – Т., 1974. – С. 8.; Чутбаев М.Р. Даствлабки терговда шахс хукукларини чеклаш масалаларини хукукий тартибга солишнинг ретроспектив таҳлили // Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ички ишлар вазирлиги Академиясининг ахборотномаси. – 2011. – № 4. – Б. 85.

¹⁴ Уголовно-процессуальный Кодекс РСФСР (от 25 мая 1922 года) // <http://docs.cntd.ru/document/901757376>.

¹⁵ Уголовный процессуальный кодекс Узбекской ССР. – Самарканд, 1927.

¹⁶ Уголовный процессуальный кодекс Узбекской ССР. – Т: Узбекистан, 1929.

¹⁷ Российское законодательство X–XX веков. Т.8. Судебная реформа. – М.: Юрид. Лит., 1991. – С. 118-251.

¹⁸ Қаранг: Громов В.И. Акт предъявления личности на предварительном следствии. Журнал Министерства юстиции, 1914. №4. С. 1–38.

is often crucial to the case and should be adequately reflected in the investigation and investigative reports»¹⁹.

It is these procedural rules that confirm that the act of presentation for recognition existed in the practice of judicial investigation even before the adoption of the Criminal procedure Code of the Uzbek SSR²⁰ in 1959. Yet practitioners conducted it as part of another investigation or procedural act.

It should be noted that until 1959, criminologist and proceduralist scientists conducted scientific research on the fact that the act of showing for recognition should have the status of an investigative act, that it is felt necessary to conduct it in the process of proof and that it should be regulated in practice through the law of criminal procedure.

Including G.I. Kocharov defended his candidate's thesis entitled "Theoretical and practical issues of presentation for recognition in the preliminary investigation" was protected in 1956, the dissertation student tried to justify the existence of a separate investigative act of presentation for recognition and its goals and objectives in this case ²¹.

In procedural legal documents, presentation for recognition as an investigative action was covered together with the investigative action of confrontation for the first time in Chapter 11 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Uzbek SSR of 1959²².

Besides, apart from the face-to-face investigation action in this chapter, the investigative action of the investigation of testimony at the scene of the incident, which is defined as a separate independent investigative action in accordance with the current Criminal Procedure Code it is also placed in Article 142¹ (examination of evidence at the scene of the incident) which is not specified in the title of the chapter.

According to the analysis of the scientific research on the investigative act of presentation for recognition in other countries of the former SSR and the opinions expressed by scientists studying the stages of development of procedural rules related to this investigative act, it is observed that most of the literature contains conclusions that this investigative act did not exist and was not implemented until 1960²³. These sources try to prove that the investigative act of

¹⁹ Бурька Д.А., Решняк М.Г. Предъявление для опознания: уголовно-процессуальный и криминалистический аспекты: Монография. – М.: Международный юридический институт, 2011. – С. 7.

²⁰ Қаранг: Уголовно-процессуальный кодекс Узбекской ССР. –Т. 1978. – С.80.

²¹ Кочаров Г.И. Вопросы теории и практики предъявления для опознания на предварительном следствии. Дисс. ... канд. юрид. наук. М., 1956.

²² Қаранг: Уголовно-процессуальный кодекс Узбекской ССР. –Т. 1978. – С.80.

²³ Следственные действия [Электронный ресурс]: пособие / Ю.П. Шкаплеров, И.В. Данько; М-во внутр. дел Респ. Беларусь, учреждение образования «Могилевский институт Министерства внутренних дел Республики Беларусь». – Могилев: Могилев. институт МВД, 2017. – Режим доступа: http://www.institutemvd.by/images/NIO/Sledstvennie_deistvia_Shkaplerov_Danko.pdf.

presentation for recognition was first provided for in the Code of Criminal Procedure of the RSFSR adopted in 1960. However, there are opinions that the investigative act of showing for recognition is carried out as part of interrogation²⁴ as a procedural action in some literature. On the other hand it is shown that this action is carried out as part of the investigative act of confronting²⁵.

In the opinions confirming that the investigative action of showing for identification was part of the investigative action of face-to-face investigation, they emphasize that as a result of this investigative action, only people were shown for recognition and according to the results of face-to-face examination, only the part of the testimony given in the previous interrogation aimed at identifying person was examined²⁶.

The opinion confirming that the investigative act of showing for recognition was a part of interrogation as a procedural act was put forward by M.S. Strogovich distinguished the type and noted that the first is the identification (determine the accuracy) of people and the second is the identification of things²⁷.

A similar idea later I.M. It was also stated by Gutkin, who also tried to explain the investigative act as a form of questioning of a witness, according to its legal nature²⁸.

During the interrogation, the subjects of the evidence determined the identity of the people and things by showing them to the witnesses and in this way, the exculpatory and incriminating evidences important for the case were collected.

Moreover, the ordinary questioning conducted by the inquisitors and detectives and the questioning aimed at identifying the people and things were different from each other and the questioning aimed at identifying the people and things were not only the people or things, but also the corpses and animals for identification in those days²⁹.

²⁴ Гущина К.А. Историко-правовой аспект развития предъявления для опознания // Молодой ученый. — 2019. — №36. — С. 88-91. — URL <https://moluch.ru/archive/274/60697/> (дата обращения: 29.12.2019).

²⁵ Михайлов А.Е. Предъявление для опознания: Уголовно-процессуальный и криминалистический аспекты: Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата юридических наук [Электронный ресурс]. Режим доступа: <http://www.dslib.net/kriminal-process/predjavlenie-dlja-opoznaniya-ugolovno-processualnyj-i-kriminalisticheskij-aspektu.html> (дата обращения: 24.12.2019).

²⁶ Қаранг: Миньковский Г.М. Теория доказательств в советском уголовном процессе. Отв. редактор Н.В.Жогин, изд. 2-е исправленное и дополненное, М., «Юрид. лит.», 1973. — С. 13.

²⁷ Қаранг: Строгович М.С. Уголовный процесс / М. С. Строгович. — М.: Госюриздат, 1944. — С. 83-84.

²⁸ Қаранг: Гуткин И.М. Советский уголовный процесс / И.М.Гуткин, Л.А.Мариупольский, И.И.Шереметьев. — М.: Госюриздат. — 1960. — С. 160-161.

²⁹ Қаранг: Гущина К.А. Историко-правовой аспект развития предъявления для опознания // Молодой ученый. — 2019. — №36. — С. 88-91. — URL

These opinions support the idea that the development trends of presentation for recognition begins with the investigative action of interrogation and this procedural action was used in the process of proof as a type of interrogation and later it was separated by the legislator into a separate investigative action after the scope of its purpose and tasks to be solved expanded.

Before the adoption of codified laws, judges working on the basis of Shariah and customary norms collected evidence through detailed questioning of witnesses and plaintiffs and defendants in criminal cases and in the course of this questioning, they identified cases in which people and objects were shown to witnesses and recognized or not recognized at all.

It should be noted that in the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Uzbek SSR of 1959, identification was defined as an investigative action, but the fact that it was not allocated a separate chapter and placed in one chapter with other investigative actions reduced the possibility of its more active use in judicial investigation practice.

Therefore, a comparison study of the procedural regulation of presentation for recognition provides to allow to note some general and special cases for in the current Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the preliminary investigation stage with the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Uzbek SSR of 1959.

First of all, the legislator did not place identification testimony in the same chapter as before and the investigation at the scene of the incident, but divided them into separate chapters and thus emphasized the independence of these investigative actions.

Secondly, the grounds of presentation for recognition are separated into a separate article and clearly defined.

However, the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Uzbek SSR of 1959 did not specify the grounds for conducting this investigation;

Thirdly, only the investigator is specified in the 1959 Code of Criminal Procedure of the Uzbek SSR as the subject authorized to conduct a presentation for recognition. But according to the current Code of Criminal Procedure, in addition to the investigator, the indicated procedural action can be carried out by the prosecutor, the head of the investigation department, the investigator, and the official of the body conducting the pre-investigation investigation.

Fourth, the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Uzbekistan SSR of 1959 did not pay attention to ensuring the safety of the recognizer. This issue is defined in the current Code of Criminal Procedure and a special procedural rule is established that according to the decision of the investigator, investigator, prosecutor or the court, the recogniser can be seen in exceptional circumstances (Article 127, paragraph 6 of the Code of Criminal Procedure).

Fifth, the 1959 Uzbek SSR Code of Criminal Procedure, unlike the current Code of Criminal Procedure does not specify procedural rules for presenting a dead body for identification.

Sixth, if the witnesses and victims participate as recognizants in the 1959 Uzbek SSR Code of Criminal Procedure, they should be notified before the investigation of the recognizance for refusing to testify and for false testimony, the procedural rules of the chapter regulating recognizance (Article 140) is defined in itself. This means that the investigative act of showing for recognition is mandatory for these subjects in the criminal proceedings.

